

Table 1. Code, description, and properties of the defect types (SZ: size, E: extent, C.L.: circumferential location).

Code	Defect name	Description	SZ.	E.	C.L.
B	Blocked pipe	Obstructions that reduce the diameter by more than 50%.			
CC	Cracking Circumferential	Cracking at right angles to the pipe axis.	X		X
CL	Cracking Longitudinal	Cracking parallel to the pipe axis.	X	X	X
CM	Cracking Multiple	Cracking in multiple directions.	X	X	X
DE	Debris Silty	Deposits of silt, sand, mud, or gravel in the pipe.	X	X	
DF	Deformed Pipe	Deformation in rigid pipe.	X	X	X
DG	Debris Greasy	Fat, scale, and other adhering material.	X	X	X
DP	Dipped Pipe	Sag in the pipe causing water to pond.	X	X	
ED	Encrustation Deposits	Deposits from evaporated groundwater with dissolved salts/minerals.	X	X	X
EX	Exfiltration	Visible flow of water out of the pipe.	X		X
IP	Infiltration Present	Visible infiltration through a pipe defect.	X		X
JD	Joint Displaced	Pipe segments have a vertical or horizontal displaced to each other.	X		X
JF	Joint Faulty	Sealing or physical joint defects.	X		X
JO	Joint Open	Pipes segments are displaced longitudinally.	X		X
LF	Lateral Sealing Faulty	Joint sealing defects or physical damage to lateral connections.	X		X
LP	Lateral Protruding	Pipe is protruding into the inspected pipe	X		X
LX	Lateral Problem	Defects in the lateral pipe.	X		X
MHJ	Manhole Joint Faulty	The bond between the pipe and manhole is faulty.			X
OP	Obstruction Permanent	Fixed object causing obstruction.	X		X
OT	Obstruction Temporary	Potentially removable obstruction.	X		X
PB	Pipe Broken	Pipe broken into blocks by cracks forming a mosaic pattern.	X	X	X
PF	Deformed Plastic Pipe	Deformation in plastic pipe.	X	X	X
PH	Pipe Holed	Hole made in the pipe.	X	X	X
PL	Protective Lining Defective	The lining of a pipe is defective.	X	X	X
RI	Root Intrusion	Tree roots entering the pipe through a defect.	X		X
SD	Surface Damage	Damage in the inside surface of the pipe.	X	X	X
SV	Soil Visible	The soil is visible through a defect.		X	X
TM	Tomo	Cavity outside the pipe is visible through a defect.		X	X